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HOW TO HANDLE WITH PHYSICALLY DISABLED STUDENTS

Allaberganova Dilfuza Ilyasovna

English Instructor

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

***Abstract:** This article explores students with disabilities and challenges they face in educational establishments during particular occasions. The author reviews the literature to find out relevant sources that support the inclusion of students into general education classes. There are also some recommendations for educators and administration of educational settings to consider in their future decisions regarding students with disabilities.*

***Key words:** physically disabled students, remarks, readiness, motivation*

Introduction

Not all classes are equal with the same student backgrounds. Some are graduates of top schools with big achievements in examinations and maybe sports, others have low level of English proficiency or poor performance in learning and many others hardly learn subjects at universities due to disabilities. No one is perfect, so we should respect each other.

However, it is so sad to learn that in some educational institutions, some academic staff and even some students without disabilities do not show sympathy to students with mental and physical impairment. The same instructional materials are used with all students. Assessments are also the same. Disabled students also want to pursue a career and achieve big dreams as other students without disabilities. But they cannot be treated similarly as normal students. They did not opt to be physically or

mentally disabled. Life is full of expected events, so they did not choose to lead life like this. I would love our academic staff to rethink and reevaluate their instructional materials and design materials that suit students' learning styles and their mental and physical situations.

Literature review

Learners with some mental, physical, learning or psychological problems are called students with disabilities. As Watson (2022) points out, students with physical disabilities want to be successful as any student in the classroom. Other students notice the differences and this may lead to misbehavior towards them. Teachers are main role players in this situation. Their task should be to encourage everybody to study, avoid wrong behavior, and raise awareness of understanding, acceptance and tolerance.

Bailey (2018) gives an example of a physical disability in students. Dyslexia is a language learning disorder found in most students. Students with dyslexia have a difficulty with reading. They are not able to recognize some letter shapes. As a result, they are not good at writing. The researcher states that students with dyslexia can think about a topic and tell you what think about it, but they may have difficulties in expressing in written form.

Watson (2022) suggests nine strategies to help physically disabled students.

1. These students should feel support from teachers, so instructors ought to identify their strengths and use them to encourage them to learn. Disabled students have the right to succeed.
2. Always teachers should expect big achievements from them. For this, they need to show their interest in these students and support them always. Students should know that teachers' expectations of them is high.
3. Teachers always should be aware of students' weaknesses. If they need more information about students, they can ask they in person. Knowing more information about their disability can help instructors redesign their instructional materials.

4. Teachers ought to be careful with remarks addressed at disabled students from those who are not disabled. Other children must understand that disabled children have the right to be respected and listened. There is no room for rude comments and teasing from peers.
5. Complimenting on student's appearance is vital because they feel being part of all good remarks. Teachers' attention to outfit, hair style can create positive atmosphere in the classroom.
6. Creating environment for student's active participation is paramount. If there is a need to modification in class management, material design, it needs to be implemented.
7. There should not be any pity from teachers' side, since it can lead to demotivation from physically disabled students. They don't want to be felt pitied or isolated from their peers.
8. Use any chance to talk about students with physical disability when they are absent. In this way, other students will understand and accept the reality and show their sympathy.
9. Find time to talk to students with disability in person. Listen to them carefully and ask for their remarks, feedback regarding classroom activities, problems and so on.

In the study by Godovnikova et al. (2019) students with disabilities showed no motivation for research activities because of the issues related to self-regulation, internal well-being and personal goals. As a result, they developed a psychological tool to check students' willingness to do activities. The researchers suggested developing a framework that encourage employers to interact in order to help students with disabilities to be successful in science, technology and innovation (Godovnikova et al. 2019).

Another study by Magedi et al. (2023) reveals that students with disabilities were disadvantaged by online learning and teaching during the pandemic COVID 19. The pandemic showed new challenges for teachers and disabled students experienced a lot

of hardship in online platform. Another disadvantage was concerned with assessments. Students with disabilities and without were equal in doing the same tasks within allocated time for everybody. Some academic staff were not fair with students with disabilities in terms of additional time, projects, etc. Magedi et al. (2023) believe that students with disabilities benefit from online learning and teaching only if academic staff and Disability Centre work collaboratively.

Conclusion

To sum up, I hope these ideas in the article will give some clues to teachers who frequently or rarely meet students with physical and mental disability. Every human being regardless of their mental, physical and educational backgrounds deserve quality education and equal appreciation. Thus, academic staff and other stakeholders must do their best to help students with disabilities.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should design instructional materials that encompass all students' learning styles. Some students are introverts who tend to be silent and less talkative. Others are extrovert who love to speak a lot and are sociable. It is a good idea to incorporate activities which involve a variety of skills including speaking, writing, listening and reading.
2. Spending additional time on students with disabilities can be useful for both sides. Teachers will explore the strengths and weaknesses of disabled students, while students will become more open and feel less isolated.
3. Students without physical and mental impairment should be taught how to behave in the classroom, respect others and be nice. Exemplary videos can be helpful to understand and show sympathy to other students. Some students do not understand the feelings and emotions of other students. Therefore, videos where students with mental disability are illustrated can be helpful. Only selective videos can be used. Not any kinds of videos help to prevent students from disrespecting other students.

4. Academic staff and other stakeholders should meet regularly to discuss the problems in the classroom. This method will help all students and teachers alike. All issues will be solved instantly. The meetings should focus on how to handle with students with disabilities and what can be implemented to approach diplomatically.
5. Parents of both students with and without mental and physical impairment can meet or network online to find solutions to issues in the classroom.

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